

UARS

Upper Atmosphere Research Satellite

Understanding Our Atmosphere

U A R S

(COVER) Model of UARS superimposed upon the STS-41 cockpit view of the Mozambique Channel, Madagascar.

(ABOVE) UARS on the arm of Space Shuttle Discovery over the Atlantic Ocean, September 14, 1991. (Courtesy of NASA/Johnson Space Center)

UARS Instruments

Chemical Measurements

CLAES	Cryogen Limb Array Etalon Spectrometer
HALOE	Halogen Occultation Experiment
ISAMS	Improved Stratospheric and Mesospheric Sounder
MLS	Microwave Limb Sounder

Wind Measurements

HRDI	High Resolution Doppler Imager
WINDII	Wind Imaging Interferometer

Solar Measurements

ACRIM II	Active Cavity Radiometer Irradiance Monitor
SOLSTICE	Solar/Stellar Irradiance Comparison Experiment
SUSIM	Solar Ultraviolet Spectral Irradiance Monitor

Energetic Particle Measurements

PEM	Particle Environment Monitor
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UARS Spacecraft

On September 14, 1991, UARS was deployed from the NASA Space Shuttle Discovery (STS-48), 2 days after launch.

Orbit Altitude:	585 kilometers
Inclination:	57.0 degrees
Orbital Period:	96 minutes
Weight:	6,804 kilograms

NASA's Upper Atmosphere Research Satellite (UARS), launched in 1991, was the first satellite dedicated entirely to increasing our understanding of the chemistry and dynamics of Earth's stratosphere and mesosphere.

Throughout its remarkable mission, UARS made observations that led to major scientific discoveries. UARS confirmed the role of chlorofluorocarbons (CFC's) in ozone depletion and clarified chemical processes that cause the Antarctic ozone hole. These are the same chemical processes that lead to a smaller Arctic ozone loss.

UARS made the first global measurements of the key stratospheric gases chlorine nitrate (ClONO_2), chlorine monoxide (ClO), hydrogen fluoride (HF), hydrogen chloride (HCl), and dinitrogen pentoxide (N_2O_5). These measurements, along with measurements of nitric oxide (NO), nitrogen dioxide (NO_2), and nitric acid (HNO_3), provide a comprehensive picture of stratospheric photochemical processes involved in ozone depletion.

UARS provided the first comprehensive mapping of volcanic aerosol layers and documented the slow decrease in aerosol amounts following the eruption of Mt. Pinatubo in the Philippines.

UARS gave us the first global picture of the atmospheric tides, a clearer understanding of solar ultraviolet (UV) variations, insight into the relationship between upper tropospheric water vapor and climate, and multiyear information on the transport of trace gases into the stratosphere.

UARS was designed to make comprehensive observations of the upper atmosphere for 18 months. More than 7 years after launch, UARS continues its observations with 8 of its 10 instruments. UARS is still taking data that help us to understand our environment and the factors that influence it.

Providing a Clearer Understanding of Atmospheric Dynamics & Chemistry

The temperature of the atmosphere is used to classify its regions. In the troposphere temperatures *decrease* with height. In the stratosphere temperatures *increase* with height because of heating by the ozone layer. The tropopause (lower dashed line) divides the stratosphere from the troposphere. The stratopause (upper dashed line) divides the stratosphere from the mesosphere, where temperatures again *decrease* with height. The middle atmosphere includes the stratosphere and the mesosphere.

Atmospheric chemistry is partially controlled by the transport of trace gases and temperature. Air rises into the stratosphere through equatorial thunderstorms and descends at the poles during fall and winter. Thin ice clouds form in the coldest regions of the stratosphere and mesosphere. Plumes from explosive volcanoes can reach stratospheric altitudes.

UARS has provided the most scientifically comprehensive picture of Earth's upper atmospheric chemistry and dynamics. UARS measures source gases, reservoir gases, and radicals, as well as winds, solar energy, and energetic particles that affect ozone chemistry.

Wherever the Sun shines in the upper atmosphere, ozone is being created from oxygen molecules and UV radiation. Most of the Sun's UV radiation does not reach Earth's surface because oxygen (O_2) and ozone (O_3) molecules in the stratosphere absorb solar UV, which energizes the molecules, causing them to break apart. The oxygen (O) atoms combine with oxygen molecules to form ozone. When UV radiation is absorbed by ozone, the ozone

molecule breaks into an oxygen molecule and an oxygen atom. The oxygen atom usually recombines with another oxygen molecule to re-form ozone.

Ozone production by UV radiation is balanced by ozone loss. One type of loss occurs when oxygen atoms react with ozone, producing two oxygen molecules. Ozone is also destroyed by highly reactive compounds called radicals. These radicals contain hydrogen, nitrogen, chlorine, or bromine atoms. The radicals destroy ozone through catalytic cycles. These cycles are important because the radicals are not consumed in the catalytic cycles. Therefore very small concentrations of radicals can destroy large amounts of ozone.

Methane

Sulfur

Nitrous oxide

Halocarbons

Natural and Man-made Pollutants that Affect the Ozone Layer

The Ozone Layer

Satellite measurements show that ozone amounts vary with altitude and latitude. The colors indicate the ozone mixing ratio (the ratio of ozone molecules to air molecules in parts per million by volume (ppmv)). The ozone layer, light blue to red, is between ~12–50 km at all latitudes. The peak concentration of ozone in the stratosphere rarely exceeds 12 ozone molecules per million air molecules.

The arrows indicate that source gases that rise from the troposphere into the stratosphere eventually form radicals. Radicals can destroy ozone or can react with each other to form reservoir gases that do not destroy ozone.

Stratospheric chemical reactions can be accelerated by the presence of polar stratospheric clouds and sulfate aerosols. Stratospheric sulfate aerosols come from sulfur compounds and volcanic injection of sulfur dioxide (SO₂).

UARS measures the radicals ClO, NO, and NO₂. Radicals come from natural and man-made stable molecules, called source gases. Source gases are broken apart by UV radiation or by reaction with oxygen atoms to produce radicals.

Hydrogen radicals are formed by the reaction of atomic oxygen with stratospheric water vapor. In addition, hydrogen radicals can be formed from methane, a source gas that is released by decaying vegetation.

Nitrogen radicals come from the source gas nitrous oxide (N₂O). N₂O is produced naturally, but the amount of atmospheric N₂O is increasing with growing use of chemical fertilizers.

Although some chlorine source gases originate from volcanoes and biological processes, most of the chlorine source gases come from man-made compounds called chlorofluorocarbons (CFC's).

Radicals can react with each other and with source gases to produce more abundant stable compounds called reservoir gases. UARS measures four important reservoir gases, ClONO₂, HCl, HNO₃, and N₂O₅.

(BELOW) UARS maps for Feb. 15, 1993 showing a source gas (CFC-12), a reservoir gas (ClONO₂), a radical (ClO), and ozone (O₃). The source gas is depleted where the radical and reservoir gases are more abundant. Sustained high levels of ClO will lead to ozone loss. White area indicates no data.

Confirming the Problem With CFC's

UARS First: Global Maps of CFC's and Their By-Products From Space

Some people questioned the idea that CFC's were responsible for ozone loss. They argued that CFC molecules were too heavy to rise into the stratosphere. Shortly after launch, CLAES detected the major CFC compounds CFC-11 and CFC-12 in the stratosphere and mapped their global distribution.

HALOE detected HF and HCl in the stratosphere finding that both increase with altitude exactly where CFC's decrease. This measurement confirms the idea that as CFC's break apart in the stratosphere, they release chlorine and fluorine, which form reservoir gases HF and HCl.

Until recently, both stratospheric HF and HCl had been increasing with time. Now the growth rate of HF and HCl has slowed because of reduced CFC production.

(ABOVE) The massive ozone depletion in the Antarctic lower stratosphere (18 km) (1) is caused by the high concentration of the radical chlorine monoxide (2). Chlorine nitrate (3), the reservoir gas for ClO, is depleted in the same region that ClO is enhanced. Nitric acid (4) also is depleted in the polar region. Cold temperatures have condensed the nitric acid into polar stratospheric clouds.

CFC's are widely used in refrigerators and air conditioners. CFC's are quite harmless and nonreactive in the lower atmosphere. Carried aloft by winds, CFC's enter the stratosphere in the tropics. Once in the stratosphere, the CFC's are broken down by the Sun's UV radiation, producing the chlorine radicals that destroy ozone.

As CFC's have increased in the atmosphere, more ozone has been destroyed. Because of this threat, the governments of the world agreed in 1987 to begin restricting CFC production. This agreement was called the Montreal Protocol. The 1990 London amendments and the 1992 Copenhagen amendments to the Montreal Protocol set a schedule to eliminate all production of CFC's. CFC amounts in the lower atmosphere are no longer increasing, and their rate of growth in the stratosphere is beginning to slow.

Pioneers in Ozone Science

Sidney Chapman (left) (1888–1970) explained the basic chemistry of ozone.

Sir David Bates (middle) (1916–1994), a founder of modern atmospheric chemistry, explained hydroxyl chemical ozone loss.

Gordon Dobson (right) (1889–1976) developed the first UV spectrophotometers to measure the ozone column.

ClO Variations Over the Arctic

Each winter the ozone-destroying radical ClO increases in the north polar region when polar stratospheric clouds form in the cold stratosphere. The ClO concentration then decreases as the temperature rises in the spring. Thick white lines indicate the polar vortex boundary estimated from meteorological data. Red areas inside these white lines are regions of high ClO. Because each year the stratospheric weather is different, the timing of the ClO buildup and decay is different. These 3 years of MLS data illustrate this variability. In contrast to the Arctic, Antarctic ClO buildup does not vary much from year to year because the Antarctic vortex is stronger and Antarctic stratospheric temperatures are much colder.

Catalytic Cycle of Polar Ozone Destruction

Chlorine reacts with ozone, forming chlorine monoxide (1–3), starting the catalytic ozone-destruction cycle. Chlorine monoxide can react with itself to form Cl_2O_2 (4–5), which is broken apart by sunlight (6), producing chlorine atoms and an oxygen molecule (6–7). The cycle begins again as a chlorine atom reacts with more ozone (1).

Providing a New Picture of the Tropical Stratosphere

UARS First: Measurement of Tropical Trace-Gas Trend Information

A dramatic new observation made by UARS was the upward vertical transport of water vapor in the tropical stratosphere. These ascending tongues of water vapor measured over the course of the long lifetime of the UARS mission are only weakly diluted by mid-latitude air. This shows that the tropical stratosphere is somewhat isolated from the rest of the stratosphere.

The tropical tropopause is the gateway to the rest of the stratosphere. Air rises across the tropopause into the stratosphere through towering thunderheads along the Intertropical Convergence Zone (ITCZ), which parallels the equator. Once in the stratosphere, air moves slowly upward and toward mid-latitudes. Ozone formation begins, and the absorption of UV radiation by ozone heats the air, increasing its temperature. The slow upward motion of tropical air is seen in the changes in water vapor over time. During the Northern Hemisphere winter, the tropical tropopause is colder than during the summer. Colder air holds less water so air entering the stratosphere in winter is slightly drier than air entering the stratosphere during summer. The ascending seasonal variations in water vapor can be seen in HALOE and MLS data. The data show that it takes nearly 2 years for water vapor anomalies to move from the tropopause (17 km) to the mid-stratosphere (30 km).

Another feature of the tropical stratosphere is the quasi-biennial wind oscillation (QBO), in which the tropical east-west winds between 20–40 km switch direction approximately every 2 years. The direction of the QBO winds has been linked to the transport of trace gases between the tropics and mid-latitudes. UARS wind data revealed that the influence of the QBO can extend to 80 km.

(TOP) Deviations from the time-averaged HALOE water vapor measurements show the ascent of tropical air. Orange indicates moist air; blue and purple indicate dry air.

(BOTTOM) Air enters the stratosphere through towering tropical cumulus clouds. During Northern Hemisphere summer, air entering the tropical stratosphere is slightly wetter (yellow) while during the Northern Hemisphere winter, air entering the stratosphere is slightly drier (blue).

Equatorial Winds

UARS First: Direct Measurement of Winds From Space

WINDII and HRDI were built to measure winds from space. Both instruments rely on the wind-induced shift of airglow emission lines to measure mesospheric winds. HRDI also detects daytime stratospheric winds using the shift of oxygen absorption lines.

These instruments were the first space-borne remote wind sounders. Together HRDI and WINDII provided the first complete global picture of the circulation of the mesosphere. HRDI made the first space-borne measurements of the tropical QBO winds in the stratosphere.

Equatorial Winds with AO and SAO Removed

(TOP) HRDI has made measurements of the averaged east-west tropical winds in the stratosphere and mesosphere (left) from 1992 to 1998. The lower figure shows the QBO from 20–40 km as descending westward (green to blue) and eastward (red to yellow) winds. In the lower mesosphere (60–80 km) the wind structure is dominated by the semiannual oscillation (SAO), a twice-yearly reversal in the winds.

(BOTTOM) Removing the SAO and the annual oscillation (AO) (upper figure) shows that the influence of the QBO extends into the mesosphere (80 km). Mesospheric wind changes occur coincident with the change of the QBO winds near 30 km. This coupling between the mesosphere and the stratosphere is believed to be caused by small-scale upward moving atmospheric waves, as indicated by wiggly arrows. (Courtesy of M. Burrage and D. Ortland/University of Michigan)

HALOE • WINDII • HRDI

Tracking Mt. Pinatubo Aerosol

Sulfur Dioxide From Mt. Pinatubo

Residual SO_2 at 26 km measured by MLS on September 21, 1991, just over 3 months after the eruption of Mt. Pinatubo.

Only 3 months before the launch of UARS on the Space Shuttle Discovery, Mt. Pinatubo erupted in the Philippines. This natural disaster provided a major, unexpected opportunity for UARS to study the impact of an explosive volcanic eruption on the stratosphere.

Within a few months, the 20 million tons of SO_2 injected by Mt. Pinatubo reacted with the hydroxyl radical (OH) to produce sulfuric acid that condensed to form a blanket of stratospheric aerosols. The aerosol density seen by UARS in the first months after the 1991 launch was up to 30 times higher than concentrations measured in 1997.

CLAES, ISAMS, HALOE, and HRDI observations captured the decay of Mt. Pinatubo aerosols as well as the change in the reservoir gases due to aerosol chemistry.

UARS First: Comprehensive Mapping of Volcanic Aerosol Layers

Mt. Pinatubo erupted on June 15, 1991, injecting up to 20 megatons of SO_2 directly into the stratosphere. HRDI, CLAES, HALOE, and ISAMS tracked the decay of the aerosol cloud, providing the first comprehensive mapping of volcanic aerosol evolution.

CFC's in the Stratosphere

CLAES made the first global measurements of CFC's in the stratosphere. CFC's enter the stratosphere through upwelling in the tropics. The CFC's decrease with height as they are broken down by UV radiation. CFC's are the major source of stratospheric chlorine. Red indicates large amounts of CFC-12.

CFC By-Products in the Stratosphere

HALOE made the first global measurements of stratospheric hydrogen fluoride (HF). HF is a stable by-product of CFC destruction. HALOE observations of HF confirm the breakdown of CFC's. HF values are high where CFC values are low. Yellow indicates large amounts and purple indicates small amounts of HF.

Growth of CFC By-Products in the Stratosphere

HCl is a by-product of the destruction of CFC's by UV radiation in the stratosphere. HALOE measurements of HCl in the upper stratosphere (50 km) show that HCl amounts increased steadily until mid-1997. The time delay between ground-based changes in CFC trends and the HALOE HCl trends corresponds to the time it takes tropospheric gases to reach the upper stratosphere. (Courtesy of L. Deaver/NASA Langley Research Center)

CFC Trends in the Troposphere

Ground-level CFC concentrations increased steadily until the late 1980's. After that time, CFC growth rate slowed as international agreements to eliminate CFC production began to take effect. (Courtesy of N. Derek/Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation, Australia. Data from NASA's Advanced Global Atmospheric Gases Experiment, and the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration's Climate Monitoring and Diagnostics Laboratory)

Development of the Antarctic Ozone Hole

October 5 ozone column images for every other year since 1979 showing the growth of the Antarctic ozone hole. Blue and purple indicate areas of low ozone; red indicates areas of more ozone. Early October is the time of maximum ozone depletion in the stratosphere over the Antarctic. (Measurements by NASA's Total Ozone Mapping Spectrometer)

Revealing the Chlorine Connection

Mario Molina (left), Sherwood Rowland (middle), and Paul Crutzen (right) won the 1995 Nobel Prize in Chemistry for predicting ozone loss by CFC's and nitrogen source gases. Crutzen is a UARS team member.

Winners of the Nobel Prize in Chemistry

UARS First: Seasonal Mapping of Chlorine Radicals and Reservoirs in the Lower Stratosphere

A few months after launch, MLS mapped ClO over the Antarctic. This mapping was a significant extension of earlier aircraft results, showing the extent of elevated ClO over Antarctica. Since these initial observations, UARS has continued to monitor both the Arctic and Antarctic late winter-spring ozone depletions. The Northern Hemisphere ozone depletion January–March 1997 was one of the largest observed.

Ozone Hole Mapping Continues With UARS Instruments

UARS has made ozone hole measurements since the satellite was deployed in 1991. As with previous years, the 1997 MLS data (above) show high levels of ClO over the South Pole. Exposure of the ozone layer to high levels of ClO produced subsequent ozone loss just over a month later. The white line shows the edge of the polar vortex. Since 1995, the size of the Antarctic ozone hole has stabilized to roughly 24 million square kilometers in area.

MLS measures the microwave emission from chlorine monoxide (ClO), a major ozone-destroying radical. Shortly after the September 1991 deployment of UARS, MLS measured large concentrations of ClO over the South Pole. Four months later, MLS observed high levels of ClO in the Arctic. High ClO levels are a precursor to ozone destruction. The chlorine radical ClO forms when the reservoir gases HCl and ClONO₂ react on the surfaces of the polar stratospheric cloud particles releasing chlorine (Cl), which reacts with ozone to form ClO. HCl and ClONO₂ are by-products of the UV destruction of man-made CFC's. These reservoir gases account for more than 90 percent of the chlorine in the lower stratosphere.

Polar stratospheric clouds form in the stratosphere when temperatures fall below minus 75 degrees Celsius. Temperatures this cold occur in the Arctic and Antarctic polar winter stratospheric region, which is isolated from the rest of the stratosphere by a strong band of winds called the polar vortex. Thus, the most rapid lower stratospheric ozone destruction is confined to the polar regions.

Cold lower stratospheric temperatures also occur in the tropics. However, in the tropics, air has just entered the stratosphere and chlorine is still in the form of CFC's. Thus the concentrations of ClONO₂ and HCl are too low to create enough ClO to cause ozone depletion.

6-Month Snapshots of the Decay of the Mt. Pinatubo Aerosol Cloud

Global Time Series of Mt. Pinatubo Aerosol at 25 km

(LEFT) ISAMS and CLAES measured aerosol amounts following the eruption of Mt. Pinatubo. The initial aerosol cloud (red to blue) is confined mostly to the tropics and extends to 30 km in altitude. As time passes, the aerosol cloud slowly descends and moves to middle latitudes and into the troposphere. (Courtesy of J. Remedios/Oxford University)

(RIGHT) HRDI measured aerosol amounts at 25 km throughout the stratosphere following the eruption of Mt. Pinatubo. Aerosols in the tropics persist while those at middle latitudes are quickly flushed from the stratosphere. In the above figures, red and orange indicate heavy aerosol concentrations; blue and purple indicate lower aerosol concentrations. (Courtesy of D. Ortland/University of Michigan)

CLAES • HRDI • HALOE • ISAMS

Understanding the Solar Connection

UARS First: High Resolution, Long-Term Measurement of the Solar UV Spectrum

SOLSTICE and SUSIM measure small changes in the solar UV spectrum. Long-term UV measurements of this type are difficult to make from space because UV radiation causes significant instrument deterioration that affects calibration. SOLSTICE calibrates its measurements using blue stars, while SUSIM uses onboard calibration lamps.

ACRIM II records the Sun's total energy output. In 1996 the Sun reached the minimum in energy output between solar cycles 22 and 23. A comparison of solar energy change over this period by the three solar instruments shows that UV variations account for up to 40 percent of the change in total solar energy output over the solar cycle.

SUSIM and SOLSTICE measure the Sun's UV radiation. Data from these instruments allow better estimations of the solar-induced fluctuations in ozone amounts. Changes in ozone occur because of variations in UV radiation throughout the solar cycle. Since UV radiation is screened by the ozone layer, investigators prior to UARS relied on solar-activity proxies, such as sunspot number, to estimate the solar-cycle variations in UV radiation. Because SUSIM and SOLSTICE take measurements above the ozone layer, they provide direct measurements of changes in the solar UV spectrum throughout the solar cycle.

ACRIM II measures total solar irradiance (TSI), the total energy output from the Sun. Variations in solar energy over the solar cycle may have a very small impact on global temperatures.

Solar UV
SUSIM

Total Solar
Irradiance
ACRIM II

(TOP) Variations in the solar UV irradiance during the solar cycle using the SUSIM magnesium II index. The solar irradiance declines during solar cycle 22 partially due to the decrease in the number of sunspots. (BOTTOM) TSI measured by ACRIM II. The minimum in solar irradiance in early 1996 corresponds to the minimum in this 11-year solar cycle. Larger variations in TSI occur during the peak of the solar cycle. (Courtesy of R. Willson/Goddard Institute for Space Studies)

Variations in Solar UV as the Sun Rotates

A plot of the variation of the UV irradiance during rotation of the Sun as measured by SOLSTICE. The six solar images correspond to peaks and valleys of irradiance during the 27-day solar rotation. The bright regions on the solar images are the source of the peaks in UV radiation. (Courtesy of G. Rottman/University of Colorado)

Ionization Map

The atmospheric ionization rate measured by PEM near the peak of solar cycle 22. The ionization is caused by fast downward-moving electrons from the magnetosphere impacting air molecules. Green

and yellow represent larger amounts of ionization; blue and black represent smaller amounts of ionization. (Courtesy of D. Chenette/Lockheed Martin)

UARS First: Clarified the Role of Energetic Particles in Stratospheric Chemistry

PEM records the fluxes of energetic particles passing near UARS and the x rays emitted when those particles impact Earth's atmosphere. The energetic particles come from the Sun and the radiation belts surrounding Earth. Energetic protons and electrons can directly influence photo-chemical reactions in the polar upper stratosphere and mesosphere. PEM measurements are being used to quantify the intensity and frequency of high energy particle precipitation events.

Solar Cycle Variations in Ion Production

The change in ion production rate from energetic particles as measured by PEM over an 11-year solar cycle. Fast downward-moving electrons from the magnetosphere create ions. The ion production rate varies by a factor of 50 to 200 near solar minimum (blue line) to near solar maximum (red line). The high-energy electrons can cause ozone decreases in the polar mesosphere by producing nitrogen and hydrogen radicals. (Courtesy of R. Frahm/Southwest Research Institute)

ACRIM II • SUSIM • SOLSTICE • PEM

Unraveling the Enigma of the Atmospheric Tide

Tidal amplitudes increase with altitude as air density decreases. This is seen in the composite image of atmospheric tidal measurements made by HRDI and WINDII for Feb. 1993 to Apr. 1994. The meridional (N-S) tidal wind is shown as a function of altitude and latitude at 12:00 noon, local time. Near 100 km tides can break creating turbulent regions. UARS observations are the most extensive global measurements of atmospheric tidal winds ever produced. (Courtesy of M. Burrage/ University of Michigan)

UARS First: Global Measurements of the Atmospheric Tidal Wind Fields

WINDII and HRDI measurements of mesospheric and thermospheric winds have provided the most comprehensive picture of atmospheric tidal fluctuations. Large-scale mixing of the atmosphere due to tidal turbulence plays a major role in controlling distribution of chemicals in the upper mesosphere.

UARS has given us the first global measurements of the atmospheric tidal wind fields. Prior to UARS, measurements of tidal winds were made by meteorological rockets and radar. These data were incomplete and, in some cases, shown to be incorrect by UARS measurements.

The cause of the atmospheric tide took centuries to understand. Newton reasoned that the atmosphere must have tides like the oceans, but it was not until the invention of the barometer (Torricelli, 1643) that the atmospheric tidal pressures could be detected. The first clear measurements of atmospheric tidal pressure variations were made in the tropics during the 19th and 20th centuries.

Lord Kelvin (1824–1907) (left) proposed the resonance theory of atmospheric tides. Richard Lindzen (right) solved the enigma of the atmospheric tides.

Tidal Variation in Airglow

In the upper mesosphere, the recombination of oxygen atoms to form O_2 produces airglow, which is observed by WINDII. The influence of tides on airglow is shown versus altitude and local time at the equator for Mar. to Apr. 1993. In the evening (-6 hours) the airglow layer is very bright and is centered near 92 km. As the evening progresses, the emission layer moves downward in altitude, "pushed" by the diurnal tide (arrows). The bottom of the layer finally dips below 85 km, where the atmosphere begins to run out of oxygen atoms. Thus by midnight (0 hours) the airglow is nearly extinguished. After midnight, as a fresh supply of oxygen atoms is brought down by the tidal winds, the airglow begins to re-establish itself at its normal altitude of 96 km. Red represents high airglow emission, blue represents low emission. (Courtesy of C. McLandress/York University)

The mystery of the atmospheric tidal pressure is that even though the tides are semi-diurnal (twice daily) like ocean tides, they follow a solar day rather than a lunar day. To explain the data, Lord Kelvin proposed that the atmospheric tide must be caused by solar heating. But atmospheric heating follows a diurnal, not a semi-diurnal, cycle. Lord Kelvin suggested that the atmosphere had a natural oscillation at the semi-diurnal frequency. The weak solar semi-diurnal forcing would thus "ring" the atmosphere like a bell, making the semi-diurnal tide appear stronger.

World War II V2 rocket observations of the temperature structure of the upper atmosphere showed that pure resonances could not exist, which disproved Kelvin's theory.

Richard Lindzen finally solved the mystery of the tide in 1970 by applying atmospheric gravity

wave theory to tidal oscillations. Lindzen discovered that solar heating of the lower atmosphere and the ozone layer were forcing a variety of natural atmospheric oscillations.

Although about 80 percent of the solar forcing is diurnal, the diurnal oscillation cannot propagate its signal to the ground. However, the semi-diurnal oscillation can propagate its signal to the ground and thus the weaker semi-diurnal solar forcing gives rise to the stronger pressure signal at the surface.

Since Lindzen's seminal work on tides, many elaborate numerical tidal models have been produced. However, until the launch of UARS these models could be verified only with limited rocket and radar data. UARS provided the first complete set of wind data needed to fully understand the dynamics of the atmospheric tide.

HRDI • WINDII

Expanding the UARS Mission: Water Vapor, Airglow, Clouds, Nitric Acid

Upper Tropospheric Water Vapor and El Niño

(ABOVE) Heavy smoke in the west Pacific, where lack of convection and rain caused fires, set for agricultural purposes, to rage out of control. (Courtesy of SeaWiFS)

(RIGHT TOP) Dec. 1–2, 1997, MLS measurements of relative changes in upper tropospheric water vapor reflect the pattern of tropical rainfall during El Niño. Normally, heavy rains occur over the west Pacific, but MLS shows that the upper tropospheric water vapor has moved east as warm waters formed off South America. (Courtesy of W. Read/Jet Propulsion Laboratory)

(RIGHT) Time series of relative changes in equatorial, upper tropospheric water vapor over the east Pacific. El Niño events appear as an increase in water vapor in this region. (Courtesy of W. Read/Jet Propulsion Laboratory)

During the UARS mission, new and unexpected data products were created from the basic instrument measurements. These products have enhanced and expanded the scope of the UARS mission.

Water Vapor and El Niño

The MLS science team discovered that the MLS instrument could also measure upper tropospheric water vapor. This was an exciting new product since water vapor is a key climate variable. How water vapor responds to increasing amounts of greenhouse gases determines the magnitude of the atmospheric temperature response. MLS makes this measurement in the presence of clouds, and the limb sounding technique provides higher vertical resolution than previous space measurements.

The top figure shows the change in upper tropospheric water vapor distribution with the onset of the 1997 El Niño. El Niño is a warming of the tropical east Pacific Ocean that shifts convection from its usual location in the western Pacific to the eastern Pacific. The shift in convection is indicated by the large amounts of water vapor in the upper troposphere off the coast of South America.

Lack of convection and rain in the west Pacific dries undergrowth. During late August 1997, fires raged out of control in Borneo, Sumatra, and Malaysia (figure upper left). The time series of MLS data shows that the 1997–1998 El Niño was the strongest since 1991.

HRDI • CLAES • MLS • PEM

Gravity Wave Breaking in the Mesosphere

HRDI has been observing the nighttime airglow emissions of molecular oxygen at high spatial resolution. The bright features occur where gravity waves breaking at the mesopause increase vertical mixing, drawing atomic oxygen downward producing airglow enhancement. Gravity wave breaking controls the circulation of the mesosphere and the transport of trace gases between the stratosphere and mesosphere. The strong longitudinal variations on September 8, 1996, appear to follow the ITCZ. (Courtesy of Julie Kafkalidis/University of Michigan)

Airglow Maps

As mesospheric oxygen recombines to form oxygen molecules, the by-product is airglow (enhanced emission in the visible wavelengths, see pg. 15). By measuring mesospheric airglow changes, HRDI can determine the location and extent of breaking small-scale waves, because as waves break they mix atomic oxygen downward, causing increased airglow. The HRDI instrument team provided the first assessment of global mesospheric wave breaking, key to understanding the circulation of the mesosphere.

Clouds

The distribution of cirrus clouds is key in determining Earth's climate. The CLAES instrument team used infrared emissions

High Clouds in the Tropics

The occurrence frequency of tropical high thin cirrus clouds over 3-month periods is shown above. CLAES has been able to map the location of cirrus clouds better than previous space instruments. (Courtesy of J. Mergenthaler/Lockheed Martin)

from cirrus clouds to determine their locations. High thin cirrus clouds are difficult to detect using down-looking satellite instruments, but CLAES limb sounding capability makes such detection possible.

Nitric Acid in the Lower Stratosphere

One of the first new UARS data products developed was the measurement of HNO_3 in the lower stratosphere by MLS. In the process of extending the ozone measurements to lower altitudes, the MLS science team realized that they could capture HNO_3 as a separate data product. This was a fortuitous development since CLAES HNO_3 measurements ended when the CLAES instrument cryogen was exhausted, as planned, 19 months after launch. (See foldout for a list of new data products.)

WINDII • ISAMS • HALOE

U A R S

UPPER ATMOSPHERE RESEARCH SATELLITE

Measuring the Stratosphere From Space

Brief Chronology of Ozone

Based on data collected since the 1950's, scientists have determined that ozone levels in the stratosphere were relatively stable until the late 1970's. Severe ozone depletion over the Antarctic has been occurring since 1980. A general downturn in global ozone levels has been observed since the early 1980's.

1839: C. Schönbein discovers ozone.

1881: W. Hartley discovers that ozone is a cause of solar UV absorption.

1924: G. Dobson builds first spectrophotometer and notes stratospheric ozone changes near weather fronts.

1950's: V2 rocket data determine the temperature structure of the upper stratosphere and mesosphere.

1957: Dobson instruments stationed around the world; ozone climatology determined.

1960's: Many ozone chemical reactions determined.

1973: R. Stolarski and R. Cicerone propose stratospheric chlorine catalytic cycle.

1974: F. S. Rowland and M. Molina hypothesize that CFC's entering the stratosphere will release reactive chlorine that will destroy ozone.

1976: J. Anderson and colleagues make first measurement of ClO in the stratosphere.

1984: J. Farman discovers growing ozone hole over the Antarctic. From September to mid-November, ozone concentrations over Halley

Bay, Antarctica, decline 40 percent from levels measured during the 1980's.

1985: NASA's Nimbus 7 TOMS maps the extent of the Antarctic ozone hole. Ozone hole covers 12 million square kilometers.

1986: S. Solomon and colleagues propose that reactions on the surface of polar stratospheric clouds involving stratospheric chlorine reservoir gases lead to formation of the Antarctic ozone hole. Ground-based observations show high levels of chlorine radicals in the Antarctic stratosphere.

1987: Specially equipped NASA aircraft show that the ozone hole is caused by stratospheric chlorine. Montreal Protocol restricting the production of CFC's signed. Ozone hole expands to 20 million square kilometers.

1991: June, Mt. Pinatubo erupts. September, UARS deployed from Space Shuttle Discovery. CFC amounts in the troposphere begin to level off.

1995: M. Molina, F. S. Rowland, and P. Crutzen win Nobel Prize in Chemistry for work on atmospheric catalytic destruction of ozone. Ozone hole stabilizes at about 24 million square kilometers (roughly the area of North America).

1996: Complete ban on industrial production of CFC's takes effect. Record ozone loss occurs over the Arctic.

1998: UARS measurements show that chlorine amounts in the upper stratosphere are beginning to level off.

The Future: Will ozone levels return to normal as chlorine leaves the stratosphere?

UARS Instrument Timeline

(Courtesy of C. Praderas/GSFC)

Into

Satellite Missions Continue

The technology developed for UARS is being refined for the next generation of space-based chemistry instruments. NASA's Earth Observing System (EOS) CHEM platform is scheduled for launch in late 2002. EOS CHEM is designed to place a suite of atmospheric chemistry instruments in Sun-synchronous polar orbit. At this time, 8 of the 10 UARS instruments are still making important measurements, including the following:

- Expected decrease of ozone-depleting chemicals in the stratosphere and corresponding ozone recovery,
- Water vapor and other key trace gases in the stratosphere and upper troposphere,
- Solar variability and energetic particle flux,
- Winds and aerosols in the stratosphere and mesosphere.

METEOR 3M

Russia.

Satellite Mission: Provide meteorological measurements.

NASA Instruments:

- EOS SAGE III (1999) for continuing long-term measurements of aerosols and ozone from the SAGE I and II missions.
- TOMS (2000) for continuing record of total ozone measurements.

Odin (1998)

Sweden-Canada.

Satellite Mission:

Measure ozone, some radicals, and source gases.

ENVISAT (1999)

European Space Agency.

Satellite Mission: Measure ozone, aerosols, chlorine and nitrogen source gases, reservoirs, and some radicals.

Stratospheric Instruments:

- Michelson Interferometer for Passive Atmospheric Sounding (MIPAS)
- Global Ozone Monitoring by Occultation of Stars (GOMOS)
- Scanning Imaging Absorption Spectrometer for Atmospheric Cartography (SCIAMACHY)

CHEM (2002)

NASA EOS.

Satellite Mission:

Measure ozone, aerosols, chlorine, nitrogen, and hydrogen source gases, radicals, and reservoirs.

(Illustration courtesy of P. J. Messore/University Research Foundation)

Instruments:

- EOS Microwave Limb Sounder (MLS)
- High Resolution Dynamics Limb Sounder (HIRDLS)
- Tropospheric Emission Sounder (TES)
- Ozone Monitoring Instrument (OMI) (Netherlands)

the Future

UARS Achievements

Highlights of 18-Month Planned Mission

- *Quantifying the extent of ozone depletion over the polar regions.*
- *First mapping of major chemical components of the stratosphere.*
- *First global picture of the atmospheric tide.*
- *Documenting the chemical changes in the stratosphere after the eruption of Mt. Pinatubo.*
- *First measurement of the descent of mesospheric air into the polar winter stratosphere.*
- *First microwave limb measurements of upper tropospheric water vapor, including regions obscured by clouds.*
- *First measurement of stratospheric and mesospheric winds from space.*

Highlights of Extended Mission

- *Observing a decrease in upper stratospheric HF and HCl as CFC concentrations decrease due to the ban on industrial production of CFC's.*
- *Documenting UV and particle variations during the solar cycle.*
- *Continuing observations of Antarctic and Arctic polar ozone depletions.*
- *Mapping changes in upper tropospheric water vapor associated with El Niño.*
- *First complete space measurements of tropical QBO wind variations and transport of water vapor in the tropical stratosphere.*

UARS Data Products

Original Product	New Product	Original Product	New Product
MLS Temperature, O ₃ , ClO, Water (H ₂ O)**	SO ₂ , HNO ₃ , Upper Tropospheric H ₂ O, Gravity Wave Variance, Cirrus Ice Distribution*, Acetonitrile (CH ₃ CN)*	CLAES** Temperature, O ₃ , H ₂ O, CH ₄ , Nitrous Oxide (N ₂ O), HCl, CFC-11, CFC-12, ClONO ₂ , HNO ₃ , N ₂ O ₅ , NO ₂ , NO	Upper Tropospheric Clouds*, Polar Stratospheric Clouds (PSC's)
HRDI Stratospheric, Mesospheric, and Thermospheric Winds	Aerosol Extinction, Mesospheric O ₃ , Mesospheric Temperature, Airglow Maps, Mesospheric O(1D), Lower Thermosphere O ₂ Density	ISAMS*** O ₃ , Carbon Monoxide (CO), H ₂ O, N ₂ O, HNO ₃ , N ₂ O ₅ , NO, NO ₂	Aerosols, PSC's
HALOE Temperature, O ₃ , H ₂ O, Methane (CH ₄), HCl, HF, NO, NO ₂	Upper Tropospheric H ₂ O, Upper Tropospheric O ₃ *, Upper Tropospheric CH ₄ *, Aerosol Extinction, NO to 135 km*, O ₃ to 90 km*, Mesospheric Temperature*, Polar Mesospheric Cloud Presence*	WINDII Thermospheric and Mesospheric Winds	Polar Mesospheric Clouds*, Mesospheric Temperature*
		SOLSTICE Solar UV Irradiance	
		SUSIM Solar UV Irradiance	
		PEM Energetic Particle Flux, Backscattered x rays	Particle Climatology
		ACRIM II Total Solar Irradiance	

* in progress

** up to May 1993

*** up to mid-1992

Acknowledgments

Hundreds of people have contributed significantly to the success of the UARS Program. Some key roles are listed here. Many others are acknowledged on the UARS World Wide Web site.

UARS World Wide Web Site: <http://www-uars.gsfc.nasa.gov/uars-science.html>

UARS Data: http://daac.gsfc.nasa.gov/CAMPAIGN_DOCS/UARS_project.html

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Space Shuttle Discovery launch of UARS.

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Key Abbreviations

ACRIM	Active Cavity Radiometer Irradiance Monitor
AO	Annual Oscillation
CDHF	Central Data Handling Facility
CFC	chlorofluorocarbon
CFC-11	CCl ₃ F
CFC-12	CCl ₂ F ₂
Cl	chlorine
CLAES	Cryogenic Limb Array Etalon Spectrometer
ClO	chlorine monoxide
ClONO ₂	chlorine nitrate
DU	Dobson unit
ENSO	El Niño/Southern Oscillation
EOS	Earth Observing System
F	fluorine
GSFC	Goddard Space Flight Center
HALOE	Halogen Occultation Experiment
HCl	hydrogen chloride
HF	hydrogen fluoride
HNO ₃	nitric acid
HRDI	High Resolution Doppler Imager
ISAMS	Improved Stratospheric and Mesospheric Sounder
ITCZ	Intertropical Convergence Zone
km	kilometer
LIMS	Limb Infrared Monitor of the Stratosphere
m	meter
MLS	Microwave Limb Sounder
N ₂ O ₅	dinitrogen pentoxide
NO	nitric oxide
NO ₂	nitrogen dioxide
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
nm	nanometer (10 ⁻⁹ meter)
O, O ₂ , O ₃	oxygen atom, oxygen, ozone
OH	hydroxyl radical
PEM	Particle Environment Monitor
PI	Principal Investigator
ppbv	parts per billion by volume
ppmv	parts per million by volume
pptv	parts per trillion by volume
QBO	Quasi-biennial Oscillation
SAGE	Stratospheric Aerosol and Gas Experiment
SAO	Semiannual Oscillation
SeaWiFS	Sea-viewing Wide Field-of-view Sensor
SO ₂	sulfur dioxide
SOLSTICE	Solar/Stellar Irradiance Comparison Experiment
SUSIM	Solar Ultraviolet Spectral Irradiance Monitor
TOMS	Total Ozone Mapping Spectrometer
TSI	total solar irradiance
UARP	Upper Atmosphere Research Program
UARS	Upper Atmosphere Research Satellite
UV	ultraviolet
WINDII	Wind Imaging Interferometer

"We shall not cease from exploration
And the end of all our exploring
Will be to arrive where we started
And know the place for the first time."

—T.S. Eliot

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